

Figure S2. Taxonomic classification of predicted proteins in the Oritaceae-classified bin 8 (CoAssembly 2). Outer circle represents species, next inner, genus, third, family which in this case is dominated by Oritaceae classified proteins. GTDB nomenclature was used for classification.